

SECONDARY HEMOPHAGOCYTIC LYMPHOHISTIOCYTOSIS: CASE SERIES FROM A TERTIARY CARE CENTER

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ABSTRACT

We report three cases of secondary hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH) with diverse etiologies including malignancy-associated, inflammatory, and viral-triggered HLH. Detailed clinical features, laboratory investigations, bone marrow findings, management, and outcomes are presented.. Clinical manifestations, laboratory parameters, bone marrow aspiration results, treatment regimens, and outcomes were documented in detail.

CASE -1

Severe Secondary Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis in an Adolescent Male Presenting With Fever, Shock, Cytopenias, and Hepatic Injury: A Case Report.

LDH	1583 U/L
CRP	60.9 mg/L
Triglycerides	540 mg/dL
Fibrinogen	82 mg/dL
S.ferritin-2500 (elevated)---	

CASE PRESENTATION

A 15-year-old male from Ooty presented with 15 days of persistent high-grade fever (104°F), chills, rigors, generalized weakness, and altered mental status. On admission he was conscious but disoriented, with irritable and irrelevant speech. No neck stiffness, rash, or focal deficits were noted.

Initial Examination

Temperature: 104°F, Tachycardic,
Blood pressure: 70/50mmHg,
CNS: Disoriented, no meningeal signs,
Skin: No rash,
Abdomen: Mild hepatomegaly

CLINICAL COURSE

The patient was initially managed with fluid resuscitation and empirical ceftriaxone + doxycycline for suspected tropical infections. Artesunate was administered due to high persistent fever and suspicion of malaria, but he showed no clinical response. By day 2, he developed persistent septic-like shock, requiring noradrenaline infusion. Because of persistent fever, cytopenias, hypertriglyceridemia, hypofibrinogenemia, and worsening shock, HLH was strongly suspected. Bone Marrow Aspiration- Numerous activated macrophages. Prominent hemophagocytosis.

INITIAL LABORATORY FINDINGS

Parameter	Value
Hemoglobin	8.8 g/dL
Platelets	25,000/ μ L
WBC	$3.7 \times 10^9/L$
SGOT	744.8 U/L
SGPT	142.3 U/L
Albumin	2.22 g/dL
Total Bilirubin	0.92 mg/dL

No evidence of malignancy

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Bone marrow smear report (3 smears received)
 Site of aspiration: Not provided
 Clinical details: Post-febrile persistent severe pancytopenia; Ferritin, Triglycerides and SGOT-SGPT elevated-? HLH
 Particles: Present; normocellular
 Cell traits: Hypocellular traits
 Megakaryocytes: Present
 Myeloid series: Megakaryoblastic maturation
 DC: Blasts and Promyelocytes 1%
 Myelocytes 3%
 Metamyelocytes 56%
 Neutrophils 35%
 Lymphocytes 3%
 Plasma cells 2%
 (There are numerous foamy vacuolated histiocytes with numerous cellular outlines within their cytoplasm—mainly platelets, RBC ghosts and lymphocytes)
 There are no "storage cells"; no parasites. No epitheloid cells.
 Erythroid series: There are very few normoblasts.
 Ferb reaction: Bone marrow particle iron status—increased (4+)
 No ring sideroblasts
 Opinion: Bone marrow cytomorphology shows a hypoplastic hemopoiesis in all the three lines and histiocytes which show active hemophagocytosis—suggestive of and compatible with Hemophagocytic-Lympho-Histiocytosis (HLH). There is no morphologic evidence of tuberculosis, Hodgkin's disease, plasma cell malignancy or metastases in the bone marrow. There are no parasites; no storage cells. For clinical correlation.

Diagnosis: Secondary Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis

LDH ↓ to 788 U/L Day 14:

TREATMENT

Dexamethasone 8 mg IV twice daily, Within 3 doses, the patient had a dramatic improvement in shock, allowing tapering of noradrenaline.

Clinically stable

Liver enzymes normalized Inflammatory markers improved

OUTCOME

Day 6: Became afebrile

Complete resolution of symptoms

The patient was discharged with steroid taper and follow-up.

Day 10: Hemoglobin ↑ to 10.1 g/dL Platelets ↑ to 108,000/μL

Conclusion- HLH must be considered in any adolescent presenting with prolonged fever, cytopenias, shock, and

elevated inflammatory markers. Prompt diagnosis and early initiation of corticosteroid therapy can be life-saving.

Case -2

Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma Presenting as Secondary Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis: A Case Report with Serial Laboratory and Radiologic Trends.

Clinical Presentation (January 2025)

A 33-year-old woman presented with intermittent high-grade fever for 15 days, associated with progressive weakness, anorexia, and abdominal discomfort. There was no history of weight loss, night sweats, or prior chronic illness.

On examination, the patient was pale with low-grade icterus. Abdominal examination revealed mild hepatosplenomegaly. No palpable peripheral lymphadenopathy was detected at the time of admission.

Bone marrow aspiration showed

Erythroid hyperplasia

Increased histiocytes with active hemophagocytosis
No blasts or atypical lymphoid cells
The findings fulfilled ≥ 5 HLH-2004 diagnostic criteria, confirming secondary HLH.
Evaluation for Underlying Etiology

CT Abdomen

Multiple para-aortic and aortocaval lymph nodes, Mild hepatosplenomegaly

CT-Guided FNAC

FNAC from a retroperitoneal lymph node yielded scant cellularity and was non-diagnostic.

Excisional Lymph Node Biopsy (February 2025)

As clinical suspicion for malignancy remained high and cytology was inconclusive, a cervical lymph node that became palpable during follow-up was excised.

Histopathological Findings

Partial effacement of lymph node architecture
Presence of Reed–Sternberg cells and Hodgkin variants

Initial Laboratory Findings (18 January 2025)

Hematological Parameters

White blood cell count: $1.4 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$

Hemoglobin: 5.7 g/dL

Platelet count: 49,000/ μL

Peripheral smear: Dimorphic anemia with pancytopenia

Biochemical Parameters

Serum ferritin: Markedly elevated

C-reactive protein: 178 mg/L

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH): 3165 U/L

Total bilirubin: 1.16 mg/dL

AST/ALT: 45/34 U/L

Imaging Studies

Ultrasound abdomen revealed:

Mild hepatosplenomegaly

Mild ascites

Gallbladder wall edema

Bone Marrow Examination (January 2025)

Mixed inflammatory background comprising lymphocytes, eosinophils, plasma cells, and histiocytes
Fibrous bands suggestive of nodular sclerosis areas

Immunohistochemistry

CD30: Positive

CD15: Positive

PAX5: Weakly positive

CD20: Negative

CD45: Negative

Final Pathological Diagnosis

Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma (cHL)

This established Hodgkin lymphoma as the underlying trigger for secondary HLH.

Final Diagnosis

Secondary Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis triggered by Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma

Treatment

Supportive Management During HLH Phase

Packed red blood cell transfusions

Intravenous fluids, Antipyretics

Empirical broad-spectrum antibiotics, Serial monitoring of ferritin, LDH, and blood counts
Definitive Therapy

Bleomycin
Vinblastine
Dacarbazine
The patient tolerated treatment well.

Following confirmation of cHL, ABVD chemotherapy was initiated:
Adriamycin

Follow-Up and Outcome

Serial Hematological Trends

Serial Hematological Parameters Over Time

Date	Hemoglobin (g/dL)	WBC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	Platelets (μL)
18 Jan 2025	5.7	1.4	49,000
24 Jan 2025	6.3	9.2	48,000
01 Feb 2025	7.4	4.3	17,800
19 Sep 2025	10.5	12.4	290,000
06 Oct 2025	10.2	10.8	282,000
24 Oct 2025	11.0	9.8	309,000

Biochemical Response

LDH decreased from 3165 U/L \rightarrow 404 U/L CRP decreased from 178 mg/L \rightarrow <20 mg/L Liver function tests normalized

Renal function remained normal Radiologic Response

Positive Kernig sign

Exaggerated deep tendon reflexes

Sustained ankle clonus

Extensor plantar responses bilaterally

Systemic examination showed no rash or lymphadenopathy. External genitalia were normal.

Repeat CT imaging demonstrated

Reduction in lymph node size Resolution of hepatosplenomegaly No new lesions

The patient remains in clinical remission at latest follow-up.

Investigations

Hematological Parameters

Total leukocyte count: 4,300/ μL

Hemoglobin: 8.5 g/dL

Platelet count: 54,000/ μL

Peripheral smear: Microcytic and normocytic anemia

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates that HLH may precede the diagnosis of Hodgkin lymphoma and serve as its initial manifestation. FNAC may be inadequate, particularly for deep-seated or small lymph nodes, and excisional biopsy remains the diagnostic gold standard. Definitive treatment of the underlying lymphoma led to complete resolution of HLH, underscoring the importance of etiologic diagnosis.

Biochemical Parameters

Serum sodium: 132 mEq/L

Serum potassium: 3.5 mEq/L

Random blood sugar: 95 mg/dL

Liver function tests

Total bilirubin: 2.0 mg/dL

AST/ALT: 182/154 U/L

Total protein: 6 g/dL

Serum albumin: 3 g/dL

Serum globulin: 3 g/dL

Case -3

Mumps Meningoencephalitis Complicated by Secondary Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis in an Adolescent Boy:

Inflammatory and metabolic markers

Triglycerides: 591 mg/dL

ESR: 40 mm/hr

CRP: 194 mg/L

Serum LDH: 1400 U/L

Serum ferritin: >2000 ng/mL

A CASE REPORT

A 13-year-old previously healthy boy presented with a history of high-grade fever for eight days, associated with bilateral parotid swelling, which resolved spontaneously over a few days. Three days after resolution of parotitis, he developed severe headache, projectile vomiting, and altered sensorium.

Pancreatic enzymes

Serum amylase: 117 U/L

Serum lipase: 98 U/L

Cardiac Evaluation

ECG: Sinus arrhythmia

Imaging

Ultrasound abdomen: Borderline splenomegaly

MRI brain: Normal study

At presentation, the patient had been afebrile for 48 hours, and parotid swelling had completely subsided.

Clinical Examination

Neurological examination revealed

Delirium

Cerebrospinal Fluid Analysis

Appearance: Hemorrhagic, watery consistency
 Protein: 3944 mg/dL
 Globulin: Positive
 Cells: Scattered RBCs, no inflammatory cells
 Bone Marrow Examination
 Cellularity: Cellular marrow

Myeloid-to-erythroid ratio: ~3:1

Erythropoiesis: Mixed microcytic, normocytic, and megaloblastic
 Leukopoiesis: Normal maturation
 Megakaryocytes: Present
 Special finding: Prominent hemophagocytosis

Patient name : Madhan Kumar Age/Sex : 13 / Male MPIN : 315010250365465 Date of sample collection : 11/11/2025 (CSF & Serum specimen)

Work up : Department of Virology, Tirunelveli Medical College

King Institute of Preventive Medicine & Research												
Department of Virology												
S.No	Name	Age	Sex	KIPM NO	Hospital	District	Received Date	Sample Type	Test	Virus	Results	Report Date
1	Madhan Kumar	13	Male	11906	Tirunelveli GH	Tirunelveli	12-Nov-25	CSF	PCR	Herpes simplex virus (HSV)	Negative	14-Nov-25
								CSF	PCR	VZV/Varicella Zoster Virus	Negative	14-Nov-25
								CSF	PCR	Mumps Virus	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Herpes simplex virus (HSV)	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Cytomegalovirus (CMV)	Equivalent	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Rubella Virus	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Epicoin-Barr-virus (EBV)	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	VZV/Varicella Zoster Virus	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Parvovirus	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Japanese Encephalitis (JE)	Negative	14-Nov-25
								CSF	IgM	Japanese Encephalitis (JE)	Negative	14-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Mumps Virus	Positive	13-Nov-25
								Blood - Serum	IgM	Dengue	Negative	13-Nov-25

Diagnosis

Secondary Hemophagocytic Lymphohistiocytosis triggered by mumps meningoencephalitis

Treatment

The patient was managed with

Intravenous fluids Dexamethasone Antipyretics

He showed a prompt clinical response to corticosteroid

therapy.

Outcome

The patient's neurological status and systemic condition improved gradually over one month. Hematological and biochemical parameters normalized, and he was subsequently discharged in stable condition.

TABLE 1. Clinical details and hematological parameters of the cases

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Age / Sex	33/Female	15/Male	13/Male
Presenting complaints	Fever, weakness	Fever, shock, AMS	Fever, parotitis, AMS
Duration of fever	15 days	15 days	8 days
Significant findings	Pallor, HSM	Shock, hepatomegaly	Meningeal signs
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	5.7	8.8	8.5
Total leukocyte count (/μL)	1400	3700	4300
Platelet count (/μL)	49000	25000	54000
Bone marrow	Hemophagocytosis	Hemophagocytosis	Hemophagocytosis

TABLE 2. Biochemical parameters of cases at admission

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Total bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.16	0.92	2.0
AST (U/L)	45	744.8	182
ALT (U/L)	34	142.3	154
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	-	540	591
Ferritin (ng/mL)	High	High	>2000
LDH (U/L)	3165	1583	1400
CRP (mg/L)	178	60.9	194

TABLE 3. Final diagnosis, treatment, and outcome

Case	Final diagnosis	Diagnostic test	Treatment	Outcome
Case 1	Hodgkin lymphoma-associated HLH	Excisional biopsy	ABVD chemotherapy	Recovered
Case 2	Inflammatory secondary HLH	Bone marrow	IV dexamethasone	Recovered
Case 3	Mumps-associated HLH	Bone marrow	Steroids + supportive care	Recovered

DISCUSSION

This case series illustrates the heterogeneous presentation of secondary HLH in a tertiary care setting. All three patients presented with prolonged fever and cytopenias but differed in underlying etiology— malignancy-associated, inflammatory, and viral-associated HLH.

Malignancy-associated HLH poses a diagnostic challenge, particularly when lymphadenopathy is minimal or deep-seated. FNAC may be inconclusive, and excisional biopsy remains the gold standard. Infection-associated HLH, especially viral-triggered HLH, can mimic severe sepsis or meningoencephalitis.

Recognition of hyperinflammatory markers such as hyperferritinemia, hypertriglyceridemia, and hypofibrinogenemia is critical.

Early initiation of corticosteroids or definitive disease-directed therapy led to favorable outcomes in all cases, underscoring the importance of timely diagnosis.

CONCLUSION

Secondary HLH is an under-recognized but potentially fatal condition with diverse etiologies. Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion in patients presenting with prolonged fever, cytopenias, and hyperinflammatory laboratory features. Early diagnosis and etiology-specific treatment significantly improve survival.